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**Re-Examination of the Effect of Constitutionalism, and Rule of Law on Good Governance
in Nigeria**
Kabiru Aderemi Adeyemo*

Abstract

Every democratic government draws its legitimacy from its constitution. The constitution is an instrument of government expressing a set of political principles about the nation's objectives ideals and legitimate process and guide the nature of political and legal order. The aim of the paper is to appraise the extent constitutionalism and rule of law influenced good governance in Nigeria. The paper argues further to discuss the canon and challenges of good governance in Nigeria. The study finds that there exists a significant relationship between constitutionalism, rule of law and good governance in Nigeria. The paper suggests a roadmap towards effective democratic good governance in Nigeria. It also examines the components and dynamics of constitutionalism and rule of law. The paper concludes that constitutionalism can therefore be said to be the bedrock of democracy and good governance, which are basically an impetus for the working of a constitutions and the respect for the rule of law for sustainable development, rule of law sustains democracy good governance on the other hand promotes and strengthen both constitutionalism and rule of law in the modern society to achieve economic development.

Keywords: Constitutionalism, Rule of Law, Good Governance, Democratic Government and Constitution.

Introduction:

Nigeria is a Federal State with a written constitution¹. The country got her independence in 1960 from England after a series of constitutional conferences. In other words, the concept of constitution and constitutionalism could not have been new in the country.

The concept of Constitutionalism was first experienced in Nigeria when the Willinks Commission recommended that the idea of Fundamental Human Rights be introduced into the Independence Constitution to allay the fear of the minorities².

The word derives originally, of course, from the Latin verb *constituere*, to set up, establish, erect, construct, arrange, to settle or determine, and *constitutiois* the noun form. A *constitution* becomes a 'regulation,' 'order,' or 'decree' as a result of some arrangement, or some establishment being made.³ Constitution like other legal concepts is very difficult to define. The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria was enacted and it became the fundamental and supreme law of the land. The constitution contains about 320 sections which established the various levels and arms of government and their powers. It contains provisions on

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¹The country now has 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended).

²J.A Sokefun, et al., Human Right Law, (Lagos, National Open University of Nigeria, 2008), p.14. I am not unaware of various constitutions that the country has had before independence ie Clifford's Constitution of 1922. Richard's Constitution of 1946 and Macpherson constitution of 1951. These constitutions apart from the fact that they were colonial promulgation named constitution; they do not contain Fundamental Human Right. Hence, they lack a basic ingredient of an ideal constitution.

³GMaddox, A Note on the Meaning of 'Constitution': The American Political Science Review, Vol. 76, No. 4 (Dec, 1982), pp. 806.

fundamental human right, separation of powers, judicial review, amendment process, representative democracy, independence of the judiciary and judicial review. To this extent, one may say the constitution as it were being founded on the principles of constitutionalism.

It spells out the following:

- (a) the aims and objectives of the people:⁴
- (b) a national government⁵
- (c) the relationship between the governments⁶
- (d) defines and preserves personal liberties⁷; and
- (e) provision to enable the government to perpetuate itself⁸

A nation's cultural and social systems, its physical setting, the state of its technology and its relation with other nations, all interact with that fundamental set of rules which is referred to as the Constitution. In operation, it must fit into the society's cultural patterns and physical needs as well as ideals and create concepts. All government and private actions must conform to it.

It is the highest law in any jurisdiction which endows validity to other laws within that jurisdiction. When a law is inconsistent with a provision of the Constitution, that law is void to the extent of its inconsistency.⁹

Methodology:

This study adopted doctrinal and make use of in-depth content, historical and descriptive analysis of following primary materials: participant observations, oral interviews and comments of legal

⁴See the Preamble of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and The Preamble of the U.S. Constitution. The preamble is usually dictated by many factors. These could be religious, historical, anthropological, ideological, etc. For instance, after apartheid, South Africa adopted a constitution to "Heal the divisions of the past and establish a society based on democratic values, social justice and fundamental human rights". This gives a reflection of the history of South Africa before the evolution of their constitution in 1996. The case of the Ethiopian Constitution of 1994 is an example in anthropological consideration for the creation of the constitution. In its preamble, the Ethiopian Constitution refers to the nations, nationalities and peoples of Ethiopia...determined to build by the exercise of self-determination....a single political community based on (our) common consent.

⁵Articles I, II, III and IV Amendments 12, 16, 17, 20, 22, 23 and 25 of the U.S. Constitution as well as section 2 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999. The Constitution determines the type of Government. For instance, while Part 1 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 is titled "Federal Republic of Nigeria", the Constitution of the State of Indonesia, 1989 in Article 1 (1) refers to the nation as "a unitary state" which has the form of a republic. In the case of the Chinese Constitution, adopted in 1982, Article I refers to the People's Republic of China as a "socialist state under the People democratic dictatorship led by the working class and based on the alliance of workers and peasants".

⁶Article 1, Amendment 10 of the U.S. Constitution, Part II of the First Schedule of the 1999 Constitution.

⁷Chapter IV of 1999 constitution of Nigeria, Section 1(a).

⁸Article V of the U.S. Constitution; Sections 1, 2 and 3 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999, Note however that these sections were hitherto suspended in view of incessant coup d'etats in Nigeria. As noted by Bola Ige during a lecture at the Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies in 1995, the first casualties of any successful coup is the Constitution. The first of each suspension came through the Constitution (Suspension and Modification) Decree No. 1. See also, Okhae v. Governor, Bendel State [1990] 4 NWLR (P1144), 327. The functions of the Constitution are (a) to establish a framework and principles of government and general terms (b) to apply to the varying conditions which the development of our (Nigerian) several communities must involve in being a plural dynamic society.

⁹See, Adigun VA.G. Oyo State (1987) 1 NWLR (Part 53) 678 where it was held, inter alia, that all rules of court which are inconsistent with constitutional provisions are ipso facto, null and void to the extent of the inconsistency.

practitioners and secondary sources of available literature such as textbooks, journal articles sourced from the library, case laws, magazines, conference papers, internet, and other works of legal literature. Furthermore, the research makes use of empirical data of other published studies on the concept of constitutionalism, rule of law and good governance in the Nigeria and African continent as a whole.

Objectives of the Paper:

The main objectives of this paper is to appraise the extent constitutionalism and rule of law influenced good governance in Nigeria.

Specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the components and dynamics of constitutionalism, rule of law and good governance.
- ii. Identify challenges that militate against constitutionalism and rule of law in Nigeria.
- iii. Explain the relationship between constitutionalism, rule of law and democratic government.

Propose measures for policy implications towards the achievement of good governance and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Definition of Key Concepts

Constitutionalism

Bo Li has described constitutionalism thus:

as a system of political arrangements in which there is a supreme law (generally called 'constitution'), in which all (particularly the entire system of government) is governed by the supreme law, in which only the peoples' will (as defined through some pre-specified institutional procedure, usually through a super-majority voting mechanism) can supersede and change the supreme law, in which changes can only be made infrequently due to the difficulty of garnering the requisite popular support, and in which there are separation of powers, checks and balances and an independent judiciary dedicated to legal reasoning to safeguard the supremacy of the constitution,¹⁰

Constitutionalism has been defined as "a complex of ideas, attitudes, and patterns of behaviour elaborating the principle that the authority of government derives from and is limited by a body of fundamental law"¹¹. Constitutionalism is usually associated with the political theories of John Locke and the founders of the American Republic, that government can and should be legally limited in its powers, and that its authority or legitimacy depends on its observing these limitations¹². It is often equated with the concept of the "Rule of Law".

¹⁰Bo Li, "What is Constitutionalism", supra

¹¹.D.E Fehrenbacher, *Constitutions and Constitutionalism in the Slaveholding South*, (USA: University of Georgia Press, 1989), p. 1.

¹²W. Waluchow, "Constitutionalism", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* available at: <http://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2014/constitutionalism/> (last accessed 10 July 2015).

The concept of constitutionalism holds that a political organization is constitutional only to the extent that it "contains institutionalized mechanisms of power control for the protection of the interests and liberties of the citizenry, including those that may be in the minority".¹³

Nwabueze has captured the whole essence of the descriptions offered by the various constitutional law experts quoted above in a relatively few words when he said – ‘constitutionalism recognises the need for government but insists upon a limitation being placed upon its powers. It connotes in essence therefore a limitation on government, it is the antithesis of arbitrary rule; its opposite is despotic government. It means therefore that constitutionalism could mean a constitutional government’¹⁴. This is a government that is conducted in line with the laid down rules in a given constitution. But then, one needs to get the message clear. A country may not be said to be running a constitutional government or practices constitutionalism simply because it has one constitution.

The content of the constitution and its operation are what will determine if a country is practicing constitutionalism or not¹⁵. Constitutionalism has also been simply described to mean a democratic government (constitution and democracy) or a limited government¹⁶.

Oyewo had this to say that

*Thus for our purpose one will proffer a descriptive conceptualization and definition of constitutionalism, to mean: a system of political arrangement that is founded and governed by a supreme law, that can only be amended by the will of the people or through their constituent representatives, in which the practice of the rule of law, separation of powers, checks and balances and good governance are observed, and the rights and development of the citizens are paramount*¹⁷

Henkin submitted that a common usage of the concept implies that a constitution has the following elements¹⁸

- a. It prescribes a blue print for representative government responsible and accountable to the people through universal suffrage at periodic elections
- b. It declares the sovereignty of the people and derives its authority from the will of the people
- c. Governmental authority is to be exercised only in accordance with law established pursuant to established constitutional process and consistent with constitutional prescription and limitations.

¹³S. Gordon, *Controlling the State: Constitutionalism from Ancient Athens to Today*, (Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 1999), p. 4.

¹⁴BO Nwabueze, *Constitutionalism in the Emergent States*, (London, Hurst & Co (Publishers) Ltd. 1973), p.1.

¹⁵This caveat is necessary as it is usually misunderstood that constitutionalism refers to following the law of a particular constitution. If this literal meaning is to be reckoned with then it means autocratic regimes (like Libya, Egypt under Hosni Mubarak) may claim that they are constitutional governments simply because they have a constitution they are working with. Even states that are democratic may not necessarily be practising constitutionalism.

¹⁶*Ibid.*

¹⁷O Oyewo, 'Constitutionalism and the Oversight Functions of the Legislature in Nigeria', Draft paper presented at African Network of Constitutional Law conference on Fostering Constitutionalism in Africa Nairobi, April 2007.

¹⁸L. Henkin, 'Elements of Constitutionalism in The Review, International Commission of Jurists, June 1998, p.12.

The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria was enacted and it became the fundamental and supreme law of the land. The constitution contains about 320 sections which established the various levels and arms of government and their powers. It contains provisions on fundamental human right, separation of powers, judicial review, amendment process, representative democracy, independent of the judiciary review. To this extent, one may say the constitution as it were being founded on the principles of constitutionalism.

Factors that Militate against Constitutionalism in Nigeria

However, one fundamental defect in this constitution which one may rightly argue as robbing it of constitutionalism is the fact that it did not emanate from the will of the people. In other words, it failed to meet one of the fundamental values of a constitution. The 1999 constitution (as amended) is a military decree and the preamble to the constitution is nothing but a false. Be that as it may, we have generally regarded the document as the constitution of the country. Despite proclaims constitutionalism, the actions and the fact that on the face value, the constitution proclaims inactions of the government and its machineries more often than not are not in accordance with the constitution. The following are some of the activities of the government that negate the principle of constitutionalism¹⁹.

There are many factors that militate against constitutionalism, democratic governance in Nigeria. These factors will be given a cursory examination hereunder:

Corruption

Corruption has been the bane of Nigeria as far back as 1983. Achebe relying on an article in Weekly Star of 15 May 1983 under the title The Nigerian and Corruption writes that: Keeping an average Nigerian from being corrupt is like keeping a goat from eating yam²⁰. This shows the debilitating impact of corruption on the Nigerian political society.

Weak Legislature

The legislature in the present dispensation appears to be a rubber stamp. This is because principal Officers are besieged on all fronts with criminal actions against them ranging from forgery, incomplete declaration of assets to the Code of Conduct Bureau etc. Those criminal charges have weakened the legislature.

Disobedience of Court Orders by the Executive

The sanctity of law depends on the respect for the judicial process through which orders according to the law are made²¹. This is very rampant during the military regime as could be seen

¹⁹Although it must be acknowledged that the successive regimes since 1999 have improved in the practice of constitutionalism most especially from the regime of late President Yar'adua (2007-2010) to that of the incumbent President Goodluck Jonathan, President Yar'adua for instance was the first president to declare his asset as required by law. He ordered the payment of the Lagos State Fund that has been withheld by his predecessor, former President Olusegun Obasanjo. One cannot really assess the incumbent President at this moment as he just assumed full responsibility not quite long.

²⁰C. Achebe, "The Trouble with Nigeria, (Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishing Co. Ltd., 1998), p. 48.

²¹DA Ijalaiye, Executive and Legislative Lawlessness: A Challenge to the Rule of Law in Nigeria, Faculty of Law Lagos State University Distinguished Jurist Lecture, (Lagos, Lagos State University, 2008), p.2

in *Governor of Lagos State v Ojukwu*²² where the Supreme Court observed that the result of the disobedience of court orders would lead to the replacement of rule of law with anarchy. This trend is still being witnessed under this current democratic dispensation despite the existence of a written constitution. In *AG Lagos v AG Federation*.²³

The major challenge to this beautiful constitutional dictate is the fact that section 14 of the constitution being part of Chapter II of the 1999 Constitution is not justiciable.²⁴ This non-Justiciability of Chapter II of the 1999 Constitution as amended is unacceptable to Nwabueze²⁵ who insists that: "when the court interprets a particular command of the constitution to be of the non-justiciable kind, it often express its conclusion in terms of the separation of powers"²⁶. Consequently, section 14(3) of the 1999 constitution remains mere declaration. It cannot be enforced by legal adjudication but would be seen as a failure of duty and responsibility of state organs if they acted in clear disregard of them, the nature of the consequences of which have to depend on the political will of those in power to redress the situation.²⁷

Poverty/Hungry Populace

There is no gainsaying that there is high level of impoverishment and impecuniosity in Nigeria. The government is not helping matters as it indulges in blame game accusing a particular party for being responsible for the poverty in the land. There is recession in the land and there is no hope of quick fix.

Lack of Due Regard for Fundamental Human Right

This has been another major challenge to constitutionalism in Nigeria. The government at all levels have no due regard for Fundamental Human Right. The militarisation against civilians over peaceful protest against fuel subsidy removal, unlawful extra-judicial killing of citizens⁵⁵, indefinite detention of suspects.²⁸

Weak Judiciary

The judiciary appears to be in total disarray especially the Federal High Courts which appears to be in rival battle among the various jurisdictions by giving conflicting orders. They are now pawns in the hands of politicians. Oluwasanmi argues that "The recent conflicting and contradictory judgments and court orders delivered by the Federal High Courts in Abuja, Lagos, Port Harcourt on the Peoples Democratic Party National Convention and the Abia State governorship logjam question the role of the judiciary in Nigeria's nascent democracy.

²²(1986) 1 NWLR (pt. 18), 621.

²³(2004) 12 SCJN 1.

²⁴This is by virtue of the 1999 Constitution as amended. s. 6(6)(c) which provided that: "that judicial powers vested in accordance with the foregoing provision of this section shall not except as otherwise provided by this constitution, extend to any issue or question as to whether any act or omission by any authority or person or as to whether any law or any judicial decision in in conformity with the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy set out in Chapter II of this Constitution.

²⁵B.O Nwabueze, *Judicialism in Commonwealth Africa*, (London: C. Hurst & Company, 1977)

²⁶*Ibid*, P.38

²⁷See *The Attorney General of Ondo state & The Attorney General of the Federation* [1981]2

²⁸See *AO Yekini, Remand Proceedings and the Right to Personal Liberty in Nigeria: Revisiting Supreme Court Decision in Lufadeju Case*, *LASULAW Journal*, vol. 2&3, 2012;

It raises concern over the consistent and persistent somersaults of judicial officers in the temple of justice"²⁹ Anarchy is inevitable in a society where misapplication of law and miscarriage of justice continue to surface on a regular basis as is the case in Nigeria.

Weak Press

The press is very weak these days. Journalists no longer indulge in investigative journalism. What is obtainable now is garbage-in-garbage-out journalism. Even citizens now pay for a piece of news to be aired or carried. This has the effect of weakening the press and stopping the press from being the watchdog of the poor masses. When a government comes to power through guile, it hardly observes limitations upon powers government.

Absence of Credible Electioneering Process

There is no gainsaying that our electioneering process is fraught with so many irregularities and fraudulent practices. This has made the constitutional provision that guarantees a representative democracy, a mockery. Peoples' votes do not always count and voter apathy, lethargy and disenchantment are now the order of the day.³⁰

Rigging of Elections

Electoral rigging or vote rigging in Nigeria is the illegal manipulation of election procedures through fraud related to ballot fixing and connivance between electoral officials and party agents to influence the results of an election. It has become malignantly a progressive phenomenon in the Nigeria democratic process and a means to ensure electoral success while subverting contemporary notions of credible, free and fair, democratic standard, or a minimum, regular, honest conduct of elections in the selection of candidates between choices.³¹

Weak Democratic Culture

Nigeria is still operating a very nascent democracy. Most of the populace are used to what is obtainable under the military system of government. Rule of law is seemingly being relegated to the background. Most orders on bail of political prisoners like Col. Sambo Dasuki and Mr. Nnamdi Kanu have not been obeyed. This is antithetical to true democracy.

Lack of Accountability, Transparency and Good Governance

In the area of accountability, transparency and good governance, the aggregate of opinion of academic writers is that the government has not discharged its responsibilities. Corruption has been the prevalent factor that is debarring the country from attaining that lofty height of good governance³².

²⁹F. Oluwasanmi, "Judiciary anarchy: A Threat to democracy" Ibid., p.14.

³⁰100 Oyewo, supra, p. 19.

<http://nigerianwiki.com/wiki/>

³¹Election_rigging in Nigeria (last accessed 26 August 2015)

³²DA Ijalaiye, "Democratic Governance in Nigeria: A Critical Appraisal' in *Law, politics and Development: The Challenges of an Emerging Mega City: Essays in Honour of Babatunde Rajt Fashila*, SAN, (Lagos, NBA Ikeja Branch, 2010); D.A Ijalaiye: *Executive and Legislative Lawlessness: A Challenge to the Rule of Law in Nigeria*, supra; M.A Belgore: "Rule of Law and Democratic Governance in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects", University of Abuja pre-convocation Lecture, Feb., 2, 2008; O. Oyelowo: 'Constitutions, Good Governance And Corruption: Challenges And Prospects For Nigeria' supra

Fearful Populace

The veracity is that there is fear in the polity. The government is using the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission to oppress and suppress opposition. A clear demonstration of this is the case of OlisaMetu the former Publicity Secretary of the Peoples Democratic Party who was arrested by the EFCC, arraigned and was forced to promise to pay four hundred million naira.³³

Illiteracy of the Populace

Another challenge of democratic governance is the illiteracy of the populace. This illiteracy prompted Ndibe to state that. "I follow public events in Nigeria with a certain sense that some grand master of fiction, versed in absurd tragedy, stands just out of sight to shape and orchestrate these events. For me, to read the pages of Nigerian newspapers is often akin to reading the most wrought fabulist fiction. Except that the events one encounters in news reports, bizarre as they may, are deeply rooted in and describe the shattering realities of Nigerians lives. These are often events that trigger the declaration, 'only in Nigeria'³⁴

Rule of Law

The term "Rule of Law is derived from the French phrase La Principe de Legality meaning "the principle of legality' which refers to a government based on principles of law and not of men. In a broader sense, the rule of law means that law is supreme and is above every individual. No individual, whether rich, poor, rulers or ruled, etc is above the law. In a narrower sense, the rule of law implies that government authority may only be exercised in accordance with the written laws, which were adopted through an established procedures³⁵. According to Prof. Diecy, rules of law contains three principles or it has three meanings as stated below:

- i) Supremacy of Law, lack of arbitrariness-the power of the government is limited
- ii) Equality before Law -No special treatment for different people
- iii) Predominance of Legal Spirit i.e. constitution as a general principle of law

The rule of law or the principle that refers especially to government under law and to an unending search for reasonableness as law's most basic norm is the cornerstone of constitutional democracy. It ensures that the state, or a set of institutions that possess the means of legitimate coercion, exercised over a defined territory and its population, exercises its power in a reasonable and not an arbitrary fashion. Proper checks and balances need to be in place to minimize the opportunities for the abuse of state power. Therefore, traditionally, the government, or the people who fill the positions of authority in a state, the structure and arrangement of offices and how they relate to the governed, has been separated horizontally into three sets of powers. The legislature makes the law; the executive implements or executes the law; and the judiciary interprets and applies the law. It has also been vertically divided into central and local levels of government.

³³It is not certain whether the money was actually paid a as the time of this research.

³⁴O. Ndibe, "Nigeria: Chronicles of Tragedy and absurdity", Daily Sun, Tuesday, August 30, 2016, Cover Page.

³⁵Origin and Concept of Rule of Law", Law Teacher , (November 2013) available at <http://www.lawteacher.net/free-law-essays/administrative-law/origin-and-concept-of-rule-of-law-administrative-law-essay.php?cref-1>. (last accessed 05 August 2015).

The rule of law is a regulative principle which attempts to define the nature of the law and conditions under which citizens live. Laws, for the constitutionalist, should be a framework of known, predictable and established rules which do not single out any individual or group on the grounds of birth, status, race, colour, origin, or any other privilege for special treatment or exemption. Such rules must be general, equally applicable to all and applied without fear or favour. The ultimate purpose of this rule of law is to uphold or defend equal liberty, particularly the equal rights³⁶. The rule of law, as clearly by Niki Tobi (2008:11), entails: a) the supremacy of the law over arbitrary power, b) every person is subject to the ordinary law of the land and must, therefore, obey the law and that disobedience of the law will be on pain of sanction or punishment, c) every person should be equal before the law. This means because the law is no respecter of any person or group of persons. The law is a leveler. This means that normally, every citizen is subject to the jurisdiction of the courts of the land. The fundamental rights of the individual, which are alienable, should not be denied him, unless as provided in the Constitution. In other words, every individual has the right to due process of the law.

Democratic Governance

Governance refers to the exercise of political and administrative authority at all levels to manage country's affairs. It comprises the mechanisms processes and institutions, through which citizens and groups articulate their interests, exercise their legal rights, meet their obligations and mediate their differences.³⁷

The Human Development Report 2002 defines effective democratic governance as a set of principles and core values that allow poor people to gain power through participation while protecting them from arbitrary, unaccountable actions in their lives by governments, multinational corporations and other forces. That means ensuring that institutions and power are structured and distributed in a way that gives real voice and space to poor people and creates mechanisms through which the powerful can be held accountable for their actions. The Report highlights the following key features of democratic governance:

- A system of representation with well-functioning political parties and interest associations;
- An electoral system that guarantees free and fair elections as well as universal suffrage;
- A system of checks and balances based on the separation of powers, with, independent judicial and legislative branches;
- A vibrant civil society, able to monitor government and private business and provide alternative forms of political participation;
- A free, independent media;

The Bank defines governance as:

"The manner in which power is exercised in the management of a country's economic and social resources for development³⁸. The Bank identifies three key elements that can be used as a yardstick for measuring good governance. These are: (i) the form of a political regime; (ii) the

³⁶Pisani, Andre du (2010) State and Society under South African Rule, in Keuler, C (ed) State, Society and Democracy: A Reader in Namibian Politics, Macmillian Education Namibia.

³⁷Committee of Experts on Public Administration, Definition of basic concepts and terminologies in governance and public administration (E/C. 16/2006/4) (New 2006)

³⁸Odunaga, S. (2003) Failure of Governance and York 200menon of Conflict in Africa. In O. J. Obi (Ed.). Philosophy, Democracy and Responsible Governance in Africa. New Brunswick and London, Transaction Publishers.

process by which authority is exercised in the management of a Nigeria's social and economic resources; (iii) the capability of governance to design, formulate and implement policies and discharge functions³⁹.

In his analysis of the concept, ⁴⁰ asserts that:

The term governance encompasses all aspects of the way a country is governed good governance has several characteristics. It is participatory consensus oriented, accountable, transparent, responsive, effective, efficient, equitable, and inclusive and follows the rule of law. At a minimum, good governance requires fair legal frameworks that are enforced impartially by an independent judiciary and its decisions and enforcement are transparent or carried out in a manner that follows established rules and regulations.

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) classified governance into three (3) political, economic and administrative⁴¹ and defines the term as "The exercise of economic, political, and administrative authority to manage a country's affairs at all levels. It comprises mechanisms, processes, and institutions through which citizens and groups articulate their interests, exercise their legal rights, meet their obligations and mediate their differences."

According to the UNDP, the characteristics of good governance defined in societal terms include the following: (a) *Participation* - All men and women should participate in decision- making, either directly or representatives, such participation must be built on freedom of association and speech. (b) *Rule of law* - Legal frameworks should be fair and enforced impartially, particularly the laws on human rights. (c) *Transparency* - Transparency is built on the free flow of information. Processes, institutions and information are directly accessible to those concerned with them, and enough information is provided to understand and monitor them. (d) *Responsiveness*- Institutions and processes try to serve all stakeholders. (e) *Consensus orientation* - Good governance mediates differing interests to reach abroad consensus on what is in the best interests of the group and, where possible, on policies and procedures. (f) *Equity* - All men and women have opportunities to improve or maintain their wellbeing (g) *Effectiveness and efficiency* -Processes and institutions produce results that meet needs while making the best use of resources. (h) *Accountability* - Decision-makers in government, the private sector and civil society organisations are accountable to the public, as well as to institutional stakeholders.

The European Commission defines good governance as the transparent and accountable management of a country's resources for its equitable and Sustainable economic and social development'. It lists a number of aspects of good governance, such as equity and the primacy of law in the management and allocation of resources, an independent and accessible judicial

³⁹Ibid 20

⁴⁰Sharma, S.D (2007) Democracy, Good Governance, and Economic Development, Taiwan Journal of Democracy, Volume 3, No 3.

⁴¹UNDP Definitions of groups/public/documents/un/unpan022332.pdf. Accessed on 12/04/2020.

system, and transparency, and recognizes that corruption is the main obstacle to the good governance⁴².

For the African Development Bank (ADB), good governance is one that strengthens the capacity and capability of the state, mobilizes civil societies and energises the private sector. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), on the other hand, sees good governance as “a commitment and the capability to effectively address the allocation and management to respond to collective problems” (UNDP). On its own part, the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), identifies 8 elements of good governance: Participation, consensus-oriented, accountable, transparent, responsive effective, effective and efficient, equitable and inclusive and respect for the rule of law⁴³.

Good governance means accountability in all its ramifications. It also means the real rule of law and an unfettered judiciary; that is freedom of expression and choice in political association.

Good governance means transparency, equity and honesty in public offices. In the Nigerian context, good governance calls for constitutional rule and a true federal system.⁴⁴

Posits that good governance consists of several dimensions. One is the capacity of the state to function in the service of the public good. Effective functioning requires knowledge the policies and rules that best serve the public good, hence, training of state officials in the various professional realms. This relates intimately to the second dimension - commitment to the public good. Where does this commitment come from? It may be generated by dedicated and charismatic leadership, or it may derive from a cultural ethic that appreciates, and a structure of institutional incentives that rewards disciplined service to the nation or the general community over the use of office for private benefit. In every modern society, however it office for private benefit. In every modern society, however, it must (at a minimum) be reinforced by institutions that punish betrayals of the public trust.

Nexus between Constitutionalism, Rule of Law and Democratic Governance

Governance is a multidimensional concept and the practice of good governance involves the following elements:

- A. The constitution, as the key source of power, authority and legitimacy, is the cornerstone of good governance. Thus, conforming to the provision of that constitution - especially as it relates to separation of powers, rule of law and due process is the primary element of good governance. It is imperative that the constitution must derive from the people and be owned by them otherwise, its legitimacy will always be in doubt and its basis for good governance be disputed.
- B. Transparency, accountability and respect for due process in government activities so that people know what, why, when, where, whom and how of the government. This would lead to transparent regulatory environment, consistent and sound policies initiated without fear or favour, and equal opportunities for all.
- C. Rule of law including the process of enacting law, the judicial, police and prison systems; incorruptibility and independence of the judiciary-explicitly and implicitly.

⁴²European Commission (2003), standard Eurobarometer, <http://europa.eu.int/comm/publicopinion/>

⁴³UNESCO. (2005). Good Governance.

⁴⁴World Bank. (1992). Governance and Development. Washington: International Bank for Reconstruction and Development. VISION 2010, Nigeria. <https://doi.org/10.1596/0-8213-2094-7>

⁴⁵Diamond, L. (2004) Moving Up Out of Poverty: What Does Democracy Have to Do With It, CDDRL Working Papers

- D. Laws and institutions that provide transparent means of dispute resolution.
- E. Freedom of the press including access to relevant information and ability to perform without hindrance.
- F. Integrity morality and sincerity of purpose in the conduct of public affairs, disciplined, responsibility and selfless leadership, the absence of all forms of corruption and responsiveness of the government and public servants.
- G. It also involves the presence of two critical elements: liberty and equality. "With these elements, men are released from the suffocating grip of the tyrannical state and allowed to fully flower, without them, men wallow in squalor and society becomes the breeding ground for vices and anti-social behavior"
- H. The issue of legitimacy of government is also relevant and this can be achieved through "popular participation in government through elections, referenda or plebiscites, social mobilization political education about the state and its institutions with a view making them comprehensible to the people, programme of social welfare services designed to make the state meaningful and relevant in the lives of the people, the right of every citizen to equality lity of opportunities and equality before the law, a sense of allegiance to the state and its institutions, a sense of community 46 and of a common destiny.⁴⁶
- 1. Recognition for good performance and public punishment for indicted public officials are also indicators of good governance as they showcase the values commended or condemned by the government.

Democracy, transparency, accountability and good governance are all concepts that are intertwined. The essence of having democracy is to ensure accountability and transparency which will eventually lead us to good governance.

Professor Sam Oyovbaire:

The problem of democracy revolves around how to forge a development process which is simultaneously participatory for individual citizens, sensitive to, and protective of individual rights, freedoms and liberty; accommodative of multiple and competitive loyalties; and generative of economic growth and distributive justice.⁴⁷

As Uya⁴⁸ has observed, though the successful conduct of free and fair elections is an important cornerstone of democracy and good governance, democratization of a policy involves much more. ⁴⁹Wrote that to ensure a sustainable democracy, rule of law, constitutionalism and good governance in the Fourth Republic, the three arms of government namely: The Legislature, Judiciary and the Executive must be restructured to make them amenable to proposed political and socio-economic restructuring. There cannot be democracy without a viable state just as good governance cannot be attained in the midst of prebendalism, piracy, indolence and ineptitude.

⁴⁶Ibid

⁴⁷Oyovbaire, S. (1999) Problems of Democratic Transition. Guardian, June.

⁴⁸Uya, E.O.(1999) The Democratic Project in Nigeria. Calabar: CATS Pub Ltd.

⁴⁹Jega, A.(2002) Evolutions of the Concept of Institutions and Democracy. Kaduna: Arewa Pub.

Consequently, there is need for therapist of the nation. This is necessarily required to give everybody a sense of belonging as a positive motivation to participate on the process of nation building. One would like to suggest a process of restricting which integrates the right to self-determination on the basis of corporate existence of the Nigerian polity.

As a policy of framework, good governance imposes demands on policy makers in their exercise of power. According to Boeninger⁵⁰ it encompasses

- i) An effective state, i.e., one that possesses an enabling political and legal environment for economic growth and equitable distribution.
- ii) Civil societies and communities that is present in the policy making process, with the state facilitating political and social interaction, and fostering societal cohesion and stability,
- iii) A private sector that is allowed to play an independent role in the economy

All the three elements, singularly and in combination, together with sound economic management in Nigeria's Fourth Republic are essential for sustainable good governance and development⁵¹.

Good governance entails commitment to the public good through the charismatic and sterling quantities of the leadership. This is derived through cultural ethics that appreciates, and a structure of institutional incentives that rewards discipline, service to the nation or the general community over the use of office for private regarding benefits. In every modern society, however, it must be (at a minimum), reinforced by institutions that punish betrayals of the public trust.

Good governance means transparency, the openness of the state business and conduct to the scrutiny of other state actors and of the public. As a result democratic administrations should manifest the spirit of accountability, responsibility and responsiveness to ensure good governance in Nigeria.

Lastly, good governance is intimately bound up by the existence of the rule of law, constitutionalism and good governance can only be good and effective when it is restrained by law, when the law is applied equally to the mighty and the meek, and when there are professional independent authorities to enforce the law in a neutral and predictable fashion. Effective government and well-functioning system require that there be clear rules about what constitution acceptable conducts in the realm of economic, social and political life.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are relevant and indeed flow from this study:

- i. Compliance with constitutional dictates: Nigerian leaders must strive towards complying with the provisions of the constitution in carrying out their daily constitutional responsibilities based on the popular consent of the governed. This will ensure the entrenchment of true constitutionalism in Nigeria.
- ii. Corruption must be tackled head-on.

⁵⁰Boeninger, E. (1991) "Governance and Development; Issue and Constraints", Proceedings of the World Bank Annual Conference on Development Economics.

⁵¹Ibid

- iii. Enlightenment of the Populace: There is need to teach Nigerians basic democratic tenets. This will extensively help the citizen in making prudent decisions during elections. The citizens must be sensitised on the dynamics of governance and policies of government of the day particularly as it relates to citizen's right, gender sensitivity, rule of law and separation of power.
- iv. Involvement of labour union and market women: There is need to get the labour union and market women involved in demonstrations and ensure that the economy is paralysed to oppose any governmental action that infringe on rule of law.
- v. It is necessary to organise the civil populace to embark on public demonstrations/ disobedience against inimical/unpopular governmental policies and measures. The need for Non-governmental Organisations: Non-governmental Organisations should be set up to sensitise the public and mobilise the populace to fight for their rights in critical sectors of the national life.
- vi. Mass Literacy: There must be mass literacy campaigns to educate the populace.
- vii. Periodic Lectures: There ought to be periodic public lectures, seminars, symposia and town hall meetings in which government officials and chief executives should appear and educate the public on the activities of government.
- viii. Restructuring the Armed Forces: The Armed Forces of Nigeria must be re-organised and structured in such a way as to obviate *coup d'etat* in the future. Safeguards must be put in place in the structure of the Armed Forces of Nigeria to prevent elements of it plotting coups to truncate democracy and they must also be educated to submit totally to civilian authority and the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria.
- ix. The centre of the Nigerian federalism must be made less attractive. Otherwise, there will continually be temptations to grab federal power for selfish economic and political purposes.
- x. There must be effective and practical separation of powers to avert tyranny of the executive over cognate organs of government or the populace.

The Way Forward

To promote democracy, the rule of law and good governance in Nigeria the following measures will be taken:

- The Nigerian government must put in place proper machinery to ensure that elections are free and fair. There must be institutions put in place to ensure that there is no arbitrary change in government either by the military or any other militant group. National economic restructuring to ensure equitable distribution of resources in the various countries.
- Government must tackle corruption and entrench transparency, rule of law and good governance. Provision of quality and functional education to improve the literacy level of the citizenry.
- To promote regular, free, fair and credible elections in Nigeria in order to elect credible and patriotic citizens into national government, as well as encourage participatory democracy. Restructuring of the judicial systems in order to improve the checks and balances of the organs of government.
- Embark on electoral and bureaucratic reforms for improved service delivery.
- Mass mobilization, value orientation and ethical rebirth of the citizenry.

Nigeria must find ways of resolving the ethnic conflicts and other factors causing political instability in Africa.

Conclusion

This triumvirate relationship is that democracy can only exist in a state where there is the rule of law, otherwise the rule of law will remain an article of faith without democracy, while good governance sustains both of them with the constitution as their reinforcing element for durability and sustainability.

Equally important, good governance involves: enthronement of a democratic government, which guarantees equal participation of all citizens in governance; provision, promotion and sustenance of the rule of law; provision and protection of the constitution; promotion and protection of the fundamental human rights of the citizens; provision and sustenance of the freedom of the press; availability of a transparent, accountable and participatory governance at all levels of government; regular, free and fair elections; as well as provision of basic amenities, such as, portable water, electricity, qualitative education, healthcare delivery, good roads, building a system that works rather than building governance around individuals and their charisma upon ascent to power among others

It is hoped that there is need for attitudinal change and leadership reorientation in Nigeria that will respect the principle of separation of powers and rule of law, constitutionalism, credible policy-making processes that is committed to the development of the entire society by ensuring the formulation and implementation of the constitution, rule of law and policies aimed at enhancing the quality of life of all the citizens to promote sustainable good governance.